

PROSPECTS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF "GREEN ECONOMY"

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Today's developing countries have in their arsenal several areas of sustainable development goals, namely, to ensure the openness, safety and environmental sustainability of cities and settlements, and to take urgent measures to combat climate change and its consequences. large-scale reforms are being implemented.

As a social and ecological necessity of the "green" economy, it can be said that the reduction of natural resources, natural disasters, various socio-political games, the reduction of citizens' attention to nature, and the reduction of trees and forests in the last decade. at the same time, it faces various problems such as environmental pollution. In recent years, climate financing, i.e., the indicator of "green" economy policy, has been gradually increasing, and many projects and initiatives are being supported by the Green Economy Financing Facility at the international level. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of December 2, 2022 "On measures to increase the effectiveness of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a "green" economy by 2030" No. PQ-436 Decision [1] was adopted, and the goals and tasks presented in the implementation of this Decision create the basis for the future improvement of the country's economy and the effective implementation of "green" finance, "green" budget projects and sustainable growth trends.

In the last few decades, the rapid economic growth of Uzbekistan was ensured mainly at the expense of resource extraction and the mining and manufacturing sectors of the economy. However, this progress has come at a high price. Due to a heavy fossil fuel-based energy balance, an energy-intensive industrial sector and low energy efficiency across all sectors (inefficient housing stock accounts for nearly half of energy-related greenhouse gas emissions) Currently, the country's economy ranks fifth in the world in terms of the intensity of greenhouse gas emissions, and it ranks first in Europe and Central Asia [2].

According to the analysis and results, it was found that the "Green" transition in the recent past is important for the most vulnerable sections of the population of Uzbekistan to climate change. Accordingly, the projected effects of climate change, including increased urban temperatures, frequent droughts,

increased water scarcity, and increased threats of desertification and salinization, will affect life in the already impoverished regions of Uzbekistan. may disproportionately affect the level. For example, households in Uzbekistan spend a relatively high proportion of their income on food - in 2016 it was 47.3 percent [3].

Today, Uzbekistan understands well the unique opportunity to overcome the limits of growth under its current development model and to strengthen its economic competitiveness in the world market, which is becoming aware of the climate and ecology [4].

It should be noted that natural resources also make a significant contribution to state income. That is, oil, gas and minerals make up about 15 percent of the state budget [5]. This shows that natural resources are particularly important as a source of income for agricultural households, and the sector accounts for 27 percent of (resource-based) employment, and the majority of those employed in the sector are poorer segments of society [6].

We know that Uzbekistan is one of the countries rich in natural resources. According to estimates in 2018, the value of Uzbekistan's natural resources per capita was 5043 US dollars. However, Kazakhstan's performance was found to be significantly higher than the average for Central Asia and LMIC [7].

The country relies on the acceleration of structural reforms to create low-carbon and climate-resilient “green” cities based on Adaptive, Inclusive, Sustainable and Efficient (MIBS) use of natural resources, while creating new jobs in emerging sectors for its economy, people and planet. Steps are being taken to chart a path to a growth model [8].

Figure 1. The distribution of green investments in the world by sector (in the form of % percentage as of 2021) [9]

In Figure 1 above, we can see that, unlike Uzbekistan, the amount of green investments in the world as of 2021 is more attracted to the construction, transport and energy sectors. In turn, we can see that the concept of "green" financing and its practice are one of the issues that have not lost their relevance in today's global environment [10].

In short, there is an objective need to form a green economy in the conditions of limited resources and negative consequences of environmental problems [11]. The transition to a green economy allows for efficient use of resources, ensuring ecological balance, creating new jobs, and ensuring sustainable economic growth [12].

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